

Supporting Information

All-Small-Molecule Ternary Organic Solar Cell with 16.35% Efficiency enabled by Chlorinated Terminal Units

Fernando G. Guijarro, Maria Privado, Shyam Shankar S., Juan Angel Organero, Pilar de la Cruz*, Ganesh D. Sharma*, Fernando Langa*.

Fernando G. Guijarro, María Privado, Juan A. Organero, P. de la Cruz, F. Langa
Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, Instituto de Nanociencia, Nanotecnología y
Materiales Moleculares (INAMOL), Campus de la Fábrica de Armas, 45071-Toledo,
Spain.

E-mail: Fernando.Langa@uclm.es, pilar.cruz@uclm.es

G. D. Sharma, Shyam Shankar S.

Department of Physics, The LNM Institute of Information Technology, Jamdoli, Jaipur
(Rai) 302031, India.

Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, The LNM Institute of
Information Technology, Jamdoli, Jaipur (Rai) 302031, India.

E-mail: gdsharma273@gmail.com and gdsharma@lnmiit.ac.in

CONTENTS:

1. General Remarks.	2
2. ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, FT-IR, MALDI-TOF spectra and HPLC profiles of FG5, FG7 and FG9.	5
3. Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) of FG5, FG7 and FG9.	12
4. Theoretical calculations.	13
5. Electrochemical Studies.	15
6. Photovoltaic studies	18

1. General Remarks.

Experimental conditions. Solvents and chemicals were purchased from Aldrich Chemicals (Milwaukee, WI). Anhydrous solvents, where indicated, were dried using a Pure-Sov 400 or using standard techniques. Chromatographic purifications were performed using silica gel 60 VWR (particle size 0.040-0.063 mm). Analytical thin-layer chromatography was performed using Merck TLC silica gel 60 F254. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded as solutions in a partial deuterated solvent on a Brüker-Topspin AV 400 instrument. Chemical shifts are given as δ values. ^1H NMR chemical shifts are reported relative to residual non deuterated solvent peaks. ^{13}C NMR chemical shifts are reported relative to the deuterated solvent peak. Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (FT-IR) Jasco FT/IR-6800 spectrometer was used ATR (Attenuated Total Reflection) method, in each case the most characteristic bands are indicated for each compound. MALDI-TOF spectra were obtained in a Bruker UltrafleXtreme mass spectrometer, using dithranol [1,8- dihydroxy-9(10H)-anthracenone] as matrix. Analytical HPLC profiles were recorded using Agilent 1260 (column: Buckyprep (4.6ID x 250 mm)). UV/Vis spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-VIS-NIR spectrophotometer UV-3600 in quartz cuvettes with a path length of 1 cm. The films for the UV-VIS-NIR absorption measurements were prepared by spin-coating a solution of the respective small molecule in chloroform on a glass substrate. Cyclic and Oyster-Young Square wave voltammetry were performed in a $\mu\text{AUTOLAB}$ Type II potentiostat, using 0.1M solution of Tetrabutylammonium perchlorate in 1,2-dichlorobenzene:acetonitrile 4:1 as a supporting electrolyte. Solutions were deoxygenated by bubbling argon through prior to each measurement which was run under an argon atmosphere. Experiments were carried out in a one-compartment cell equipped with a glassy carbon electrode, a platinum wire counter electrode and an Ag/AgNO_3 as pseudo reference electrode. All Potentials were checked against the ferrocene/ferrocenium couple (Fc/Fc^+) after each experiment. Melting points are recorded in Gallenkamp melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Thermogravimetric analyses were performed using a TGA/DSC Linea Excellent instrument by Mettler-Toledo and collected under inert atmosphere of nitrogen with a scan rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. The weight changes were recorded as a function of temperature. Theoretical calculations were carried out within the density functional theory (DFT) framework by using the Gaussian 09, applying density functional theory at the B3LYP level. The basis set of 6-31G* was used in the calculations (Supercomputation Service of UCLM).

Preparation of devices:

The solution processed organic solar cells were fabricated on the ITO coated glass substrate with structure ITO/PEDOT:PSS/active layer /PFN/Al. The ITO coated glass substrates were cleaned in detergent, and subsequently ultra-sonicated in deionized water, acetone and isopropyl alcohol and dried *in vacuum* oven to remove all the traces of residues. We have fabricated devices using FG5, FG7 and FG9 as donor and two acceptors i.e., TOCR2 and DICTF. The photovoltaic performance optimization process was started with identifying the donor to acceptor ratio and after that solvent vapor annealing was applied to maximize the performance of the OSCs. The total concentration of D:A blend mixture was 16 mg/mL in chloroform. The devices were fabricated by depositing PEDOT:PSS as hole transport layer having thickness of 35-40 nm. The active layer was deposited by spin coating (2500 rpm, 60 s) on the top of PEDOT:PSS layer under ambient conditions. After that we have optimize the device performance via solvent vapor treatment (SVA) method. The active layer with optimized weight ratio was exposed to the THF vapours for 40s. Due to the limited amounts of materials used for present investigations, we are not able to fabricate devices with SVA active layers with different processing times. We have done the SVA treatment only for 40s, as per our earlier experience on organic solar cells. A thin layer of PFN was spin coated on the top of the active layer from the methanol solution. The aluminium (Al) electrode was deposited onto the top of PFN layer *via* thermal evaporation at the pressure less than 10^{-5} Torr. All devices were fabricated and tested in an ambient atmosphere without encapsulation. The effective area of the devices is 0.16 mm^2 . The ternary OSCs were fabricated via varying the weight ratio between two acceptors (TOCR2 and DICTF) and keeping the concentration of FG5 donor constant. The optimization is done same as for binary counterparts. The current-voltage characteristics of the OSCs were measured under illumination intensity of 100 mW/cm^2 (AM1.5 G) using a solar simulator and a Keithley 2400 source meter unit. The External quantum efficiency (EQE) measurements were performed using Bentham EQE system.

The hole-only and electron-only devices with ITO/PEDOT:PSS/active layer /Au and ITO/Al/ active layer/Al architectures were also fabricated in a similar way, to measure the hole and electron mobility. We have measured the dark J-V characteristics and fitted with the space charge limited current model.

For the transient photocurrent (TPC) and transient photovoltage (TPV) decay, the device was mounted on a conductive clip under steady state illumination from the focused quartz-tungsten halogen lamp light source. An optical perturbation is applied to the device with 1kHz femtosecond pulse laser under 500 nm excitation. The TPV signal was acquired by a digital oscilloscope at open circuit condition ($1\text{M}\Omega$). The TPC signal was measured under short circuit by applying a $50\ \Omega$ resistor. The carrier lifetime and charge carrier extraction times were estimated via fitting the TPV and TPC decay with exponential.

2. ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, FT-IR, MALDI-TOF spectra and HPLC profiles of FG5, FG7 and FG9.

Figure S1. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound FG5.

Figure S2. ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound FG5.

Figure S3. FT-IR (KBr) spectrum of small molecule **FG5**.

Figure S4. MS (MALDI-TOF) spectrum of compound **FG5**.

Figure S5. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound **FG7**.

Figure S6. ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound **FG7**.

Figure S7. FT-IR (KBr) spectrum of small molecule **FG7**.

Figure S8. MS (MALDI-TOF) spectrum of compound **FG7**.

Figure S9. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound **FG9**.

Figure S10. ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) spectrum of compound **FG9**.

Figure S11. FT-IR (KBr) spectrum of small molecule **FG9**.

Figure S12. MS (MALDI-TOF) spectrum of compound **FG9**.

Figure S13. HPLC profile of compound **FG5**. Conditions: HPLC column: Buckyrep (4.6ID x 250 mm)), Toluene 100% as eluent (1mL/min); $\lambda=700$ nm; 25 °C.

Figure S14. HPLC profile of compound **FG7**. Conditions: HPLC column: Buckyrep (4.6ID x 250 mm)), Toluene 100% as eluent (1mL/min); $\lambda=700$ nm; 25 °C.

Figure S15. HPLC profile of compound **FG9**. Conditions: HPLC column: Buckyrep (4.6ID x 250 mm)), Toluene 100% as eluent (1mL/min); $\lambda=700$ nm; 25 °C.

3. Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) of FG5, FG7 and FG9.

Figure S16. TGA curves of small molecule **FG5**, **FG7** and **FG9** at scan rate of 10 °C min⁻¹.

Table S1. Decomposition temperatures (T_d) and melting point (m.p) of **FG5**, **FG7** and **FG9**

Small Molecule	T_d (°C)	m.p
FG5	334	>300
FG7	332	>300
FG9	328	289-290

4. Theoretical calculations.

Table S1. Energies in electron volts (E/eV) and main fragmental contributions (percentage values within brackets) to HOMO and LUMO orbitals of **FG5**, **FG 7** and **FG9**. CPDT1 refers to the central cyclopentadithiophene unit, CPDT2 denotes the two cyclopentadithiophene units fused to the central one, and ID represents the two indandione fragments.

Orbital	E/eV			Fragmental contributions		
	FG5	FG7	FG9	FG5	FG7	FG9
LUMO	-3.37	-3.32	-3.11	CPDT1 (25) CPDT2 (47) ID (28)	CPDT1 (26) CPDT2 (47) ID (27)	CPDT1 (28) CPDT2 (48) ID (24)
HOMO	-5.03	-4.99	-4.81	CPDT1 (40) CPDT2 (48) ID (12)	CPDT1 (40) CPDT2 (48) ID (12)	CPDT1 (40) CPDT2 (49) ID (11)

Figure S17. Optimized geometry for small molecule **FG5** (Gaussian 09W, DFT-B3LYP 6-31G)

Figure S18. Optimized geometry for small molecule **FG7** (Gaussian 09W, DFT-B3LYP 6-31G)

Figure S19. Optimized geometry for small molecule **FG9** (Gaussian 09W, DFT-B3LYP 6-31G)

Figure S20. Calculated fragmental contributions, energies and energy gaps for HOMO and LUMO molecular orbitals provided along with their topologies for **FG5**, **FG7** and **FG8** compounds. The length of each color bar is proportional to the percentage contribution of the corresponding-colored moiety to each molecular orbital. Color codes for bars and molecular fragments: CPDT1: refers to the central cyclopentadithiophene unit (red), CPDT2: denotes the two cyclopentadithiophene units fused to the central one (blue), ID: represents the two indandione fragments (navy blue).

Figure S21. Molecular electrostatic potential maps of **FG5**, **FG7** and **FG9**. Deepest red colour corresponds to the lowest electrostatic potential energy value in atomic units (hartree) and blue as the highest.

5. Electrochemical Studies.

Figure S22. Cyclic Voltammetry for small molecule **FG5**: Reduction (left) and Oxidation (right)

Figure S23. Oyster-Young Square Wave Voltammetry for small molecule **FG5**: Reduction (left) and Oxidation (right)

Figure S24. Cyclic Voltammetry for small molecule **FG7**: Reduction (left) and Oxidation (right)

Figure S25. Oyster-Young Square Wave Voltammetry for small molecule **FG7**: Reduction (left) and Oxidation (right)

Figure S26. Oyster-Young Square Wave Voltammetry for small molecule **FG9**:
Reduction (left) and Oxidation (right)

Figure S27. Oyster-Young Square Wave Voltammetry for small molecule **FG9**:
Reduction (left) and Oxidation (right).

6. Photovoltaic studies

Figure S28. Absorption spectra of **FG5:TOCR2** (—■—), **FG5:DICTF** (—●—) and **FG5:DICTF:TOCR2** (—▲—).

Figure S29. PL spectrum of pristine DICTF and absorption spectra of **FG5** and **TOCR2**.

Table S2a. Photovoltaic parameters of the OSCs for **FG5:TOCR2** with different weight ratios of **FG5** and **TOCR2** processed with chloroform as solvent.

FG5:TOCR2 weight ratio	J_{SC} (mA/cm ²)	V_{OC} (V)	FF	PCE (%)
1:0.4	16.32	0.88	0.62	8.90
1:0.8	17.78	0.89	0.64	10.13
1:1.2	18.45	0.89	0.66	10.84
1:1.4	17.62	0.88	0.64	9.92

Table S2b. Photovoltaic parameters of the OSCs for **FG7:TOCR2** with different weight ratios of **FG7** and **TOCR2** processed with chloroform as solvent.

FG7:TOCR2 weight ratio	J_{SC} (mA/cm ²)	V_{OC} (V)	FF	PCE (%)
1:0.4	15.28	0.89	0.58	7.89
1:0.8	15.98	0.89	0.61	8.67
1:1.2	16.54	0.90	0.63	9.38
1:1.4	16.32	0.89	0.61	8.86

Table S2c. Photovoltaic parameters of the OSCs for **FG9:TOCR2** with different weight ratios of **FG9** and **TOCR2** processed with chloroform as solvent.

FG9:TOCR2 weight ratio	J_{SC} (mA/cm ²)	V_{OC} (V)	FF	PCE (%)
1:0.4	13.94	0.92	0.52	6.67
1:0.8	14.67	0.91	0.55	7.34
1:1.2	15.82	0.92	0.59	8.59
1:1.4	15.23	0.91	0.57	7.90

Table S3. Photovoltaic parameters of the OSCs for **FG5:DICTF:TOCR2** with different weight ratios of **DICTF** and **TOCR2** processed with chloroform as solvent.

DICTF: TOCR2 weight ratio	J_{SC} (mA/cm ²)	V_{OC} (V)	FF	PCE (%)
1:0.1:1.1	18.64	0.94	0.665	11.65
1:0.2:1.0	20.31	0.96	0.678	13.22
1:0.4:0.8	19.65	0.99	0.664	12.92
1:1.2:0.0	14.78	1.01	0.632	9.43